

An epigenetic module common to the T lymphocyte.

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The T-lymphocyte epigenetic module included Brd4, Dot1l, Kmt5b, Phc1, Hdac8, Suv39H1, Kdm5d, Taf factors Taf1a, Taf9b, and Taf6, and Arid2.

Citations

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